

Yield potential

Typhoon injury during a date-of-planting trial in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh (AP), India

V. D. Naidu, G. V. Reddy, P. Subbrarami Reddy, and P. Sudhakar Reddy, Agricultural Research Station, Nellore 524004, India

Coastal parts of Nellore district, AP, experienced severe gales in mid-Nov 1984, with winds up to 120 km/h for nearly 60 h. The severe wind speed caused varying damage to the leaf tissue of all entries in a date-of-planting trial.

To know whether wind caused damage at different age levels,

observations were taken after 3 d of cyclone on four local cultivars in the date-of-planting trial.

The trial was laid out in a factorial random block design with three replications and five planting dates, from 20 Aug to 19 Oct at 15-d intervals. NLR9672, NLR9672-96, NLR9674, and NLR27999 were planted at 15- × 15-cm spacing. Plot size was 4.5 × 3.7 m. Fertilizer at 80-60-40 kg NPK/ha was applied to all treatments (all the phosphate and potash and 1/3 N at puddling, 1/3 N at tillering, and 1/3 N at panicle initiation).

At the time of the typhoon, the crop was 123, 98, 83, 66, and 51 d old. We measured wind damage (shredding of leaf blades from tip downward coupled with necrotic streaks resembling bacterial leaf streak) after 3 d of wind. Leaves shredded were counted on five randomly selected plants in each plot and mean leaf damage percentage calculated.

Maximum wind damage was in the 123-d-old crops, it decreased with plant age (see table). NLR27999 had the most damage. □

Effect of high wind on leaf damage in 4 rice varieties at different crop ages. Nellore, India, 1984.

Variety and planting date	Crop age (d)	Damage (%)
<i>NLR 9672</i>		
20 Aug	123	20
5 Sep	98	20
20 Sep	83	7
5 Oct	66	3
19 Oct	51	2
Mean		10
<i>NLR 9672-96</i>		
20 Aug	123	27
5 Sep	98	30
20 Sep	83	7
5 Oct	66	5
19 Oct	51	2
Mean		14
<i>NLR 9674</i>		
20 Aug	123	30
5 Sep	98	27
20 Sep	83	4
5 Oct	66	3
19 Oct	51	3
Mean		13
<i>NLR 27999</i>		
20 Aug	123	30
5 Sep	98	25
20 Sep	83	18
5 Oct	66	4
19 Oct	51	2
Mean		16

Genotypic variation in mineral uptake of rice mutants and parents

S. M. Alam, A. R. Azmi, and S. S. M. Naqvi, Atomic Energy Agricultural Research Centre, Tando Jam, Pakistan

We evaluated 18 rice genotypes for mineral uptake in the field. Soil was sandy loam, with pH 7.8, 0.12% TSS, 12.5% CaCO₃, 0.43% K, 0.094% P, 0.069% N, 0.69% organic matter, exchangeable cations Ca 34.7, Mg 3.36, Na 0.89, and K 0.38 meq/100 g soil. Standard 120 kg N and 60 kg P/ha were applied at plowing. Plant spacing was at 16 seedlings/m², in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Normal cultural practices were followed. Straw and grain were analyzed for N, P, K, Ca, and Na content.

Rice mutants and their parents differed in mineral uptake (see table). Concentrations in IR6, IR8, Bas 370, Jajai 77, Sada Gulab, and Sonahri Sugdasi were generally lower than in their mutants. N and P were higher in grain than in straw; K, Ca, and Na were lower in grain than in straw, irrespective of genotype.

Variation among the genotypes was high. □

Nutrient content in grain and straw of rice genotypes and their mutants. Tando Jam, Pakistan.

Genotype	Nutrient content (% dry wt) of grain					Nutrient content (% dry wt) of straw				
	N	P	K	Ca	Na	N	P	K	Ca	Na
IR6 (parent)	0.86	0.36	0.30	0.003	0.04	0.28	0.20	1.61	0.14	0.12
Mutant IR6-18	1.26	0.40	0.32	0.003	0.06	0.48	0.21	1.67	0.13	0.10
Mutant IR6-NG-104	1.32	0.43	0.34	0.002	0.06	0.63	0.24	1.86	0.11	0.11
Mutant IR6-NG-13	1.12	0.37	0.31	0.002	0.06	0.98	0.36	1.63	0.11	0.15
IR8 (parent)	0.84	0.36	0.25	0.003	0.05	0.60	0.13	1.65	0.16	0.13
Mutant IR8-5	0.94	0.37	0.33	0.003	0.07	0.70	0.33	1.75	0.15	0.12
Bas 370 (parent)	1.37	0.40	0.25	0.003	0.06	0.70	0.24	1.33	0.06	0.10
Mutant 370-1	1.88	0.44	0.39	0.002	0.11	0.98	0.32	1.69	0.14	0.12
Mutant 370-5	1.49	0.44	0.32	0.002	0.10	0.77	0.29	1.56	0.12	0.17
Jajai 77 (parent)	1.09	0.37	0.25	0.003	0.06	0.63	0.19	1.08	0.12	0.11
Mutant Jajai 77-1	1.29	0.52	0.35	0.003	0.09	0.69	0.25	1.43	0.19	0.14
Mutant Jajai 77-2	1.21	0.39	0.28	0.004	0.08	0.70	0.09	1.68	0.14	0.17
Sada Gulab (parent)	1.26	0.39	0.28	0.002	0.06	0.56	0.24	1.55	0.15	0.14
Mutant SG-EF/SD-78	2.80	0.42	0.36	0.002	0.08	0.70	0.21	1.98	0.13	0.16
Mutant SG-EF/SD-55	2.38	0.47	0.35	0.003	0.09	0.66	0.23	2.10	0.11	0.17
Sonahri Sugdasi (parent)	1.12	0.44	0.23	0.003	0.06	0.63	0.25	1.27	0.09	0.10
Mutant SS-EF/SD-6	1.26	0.48	0.38	0.002	0.07	0.76	0.35	1.53	0.11	0.12
Mutant SS-EF/SD-8	1.26	0.46	0.32	0.002	0.08	1.47	0.29	1.57	0.06	0.12
LSD (0.05)	0.23	0.06	0.04	ns	0.01	0.21	0.07	0.27	0.04	0.02
(0.01)	0.30	0.08	0.05	ns	0.02	0.27	0.10	0.36	0.05	0.03